

Chromic Acid Oxidation of Aromatic Acetals in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium. A Kinetic and Mechanistic Study

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When aromatic acetals of benzaldehyde and substituted-benzaldehyde with aliphatic alcohols are subjected to chromic acid oxidation in aqueous acetic acid medium, the corresponding esters are the main products. The oxidation follows a total second order kinetics, first order each in [acetal] and $[Cr^{VI}]$. The decrease of solvent polarity increases the rate of oxidation. The rate-determining step is assumed to be the elimination of proton from the complex species involving the acetal and chromium. The activation enthalpies and entropies of the oxidation of aromatic acetals are linearly related.

HEYWOOD and Phillips¹ reported the oxidation of diethyl acetals of butyraldehyde, benzaldehyde and β -phenyl- β -ethoxypropionaldehyde with peracetic acid in the presence of sulphuric acid, the product being the corresponding ethyl esters. In continuation of our earlier works on aromatic as well as aliphatic acetals²⁻⁵, we have taken an interesting series of six aromatic acetals in order to investigate for the first time the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation with Cr^{VI} ^{6,7}.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of AnalaR grade and were used as such or purified by standard procedures. Benzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal (BnBA), 3-chlorobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 4-chlorobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 3-nitrobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal, 4-nitrobenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal and 4-methoxybenzaldehyde di-n-butyl acetal were prepared by the standard methods and the purity was checked by the usual methods.

Kinetic measurement: The reactions were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions ($[acetal] \gg [Cr^{VI}]$) in acetic acid (70, 80, 85 and 90%, v/v) and followed iodometrically. The rate constants were computed from the linear ($r > 0.98$) plots of $\log [oxidant]$ against time. The results were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Product analysis: The glc analysis of the products showed the presence of n-butyl benzoate and n-butyl acetate. It was observed that 3 mol of chromic acid consumed 2 mol of acetal.

Results and Discussion

The results can be summarised as follows. (i) The oxidation reaction is found to be clearly of first

order both with respect to time (as proved by good fits of $\log [Cr^{VI}]$ vs time plots) and concentration as shown by the time order rate coefficient being independent of initial concentration of Cr^{VI} (Table 1). (ii) The effect of variation of initial concentration of acetal shows first order dependence on the concentration of acetal (Table 1). (iii) The oxidation reaction is accelerated by increasing the volume percentage of acetic acid in HOAc-H₂O

TABLE 1—DEPENDENCE OF REACTION RATE ON OXIDANT AND SUBSTRATE

Solvent: HOAc-H₂O=9:1 (v/v), Ionic strength=0.2 M, Temp.=308 K

[BnBA] $\times 10^3 M$	$[CrO_3]$ $\times 10^3 M$	k_1 $\times 10^4 s^{-1}$
0.77	2.0	2.8
2.00	2.0	7.5
3.11	2.0	11.2
3.88	2.0	13.9
2.0	3.0	7.3
2.0	4.0	7.3
2.0	6.0	7.4

mixtures. (iv) The rates of oxidation were obtained at different temperatures and the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2). (v) The possibility of free radical mechanism is ruled out since the rate of oxidation of BnBA with Cr^{VI} does not induce polymerisation of added allyl acetate. (vi) While the rate of oxidation of BnBA with Cr^{VI} decreases with the increasing concentration of sodium acetate, the disodium salt of EDTA accelerates the rate of oxidation in a progressive manner. (vii) Added n-butyl benzoate, an oxidation product of BnBA, in the kinetic runs with BnBA did not affect the rate. (viii) Since the addition of sodium chloride retards the oxidation of BnBA by Cr^{VI} ,

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TABLE 2—RATE DATA ON TEMPERATURE EFFECTS IN AQUEOUS ACETIC ACID MEDIUM AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS

Acetal	$k_2 (\times 10^3 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1})$			ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	308 K	318 K	328 K		
BnBA	3.84	11.58	23.5	73.2	36.7
4-OCH ₃	0.13	0.27	1.0	55.8	121.0
3-NO ₂	4.3	12.1	33.5	88.4	2.2
4-NO ₂	7.0	17.1	41.0	69.9	42.2
3-Cl	5.0	18.5	34.0	80.6	10.1
4-Cl	5.8	10.4	17.0	47.1	117.7

the formation of less reactive chlorochromate (ClCrO₃⁻) anion in solution may possibly be inferred. (ix) The rate of oxidation of BnBA with Cr^{VI} increases progressively with the increasing concentration of oxalic acid. Oxalic acid forms an ester with HCrO₄⁻ and H⁺ and this ester having a positively charged chromium can easily attack the acetal to form the ternary complex, which decomposes in a rate determining step to give the products. A similar mechanism has been proposed for the cooxidation of secondary alcohols and oxalic acid with Cr^{VI}. (x) The increase in [HClO₄] and [H₂SO₄] increase the rate of oxidation of BnBA with Cr^{VI}. Slopes obtained in the plots log k_2 vs log [H⁺] show that the rate dependence of [H⁺] is 1.1 for perchloric acid and 0.5 for sulphuric acid. This can be traced to the effect of the anion of these acids on the chromate ion. For the acid catalysed oxidation, the rate law may be given as in equation (1),

$$\frac{-d[\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}]}{dt} = k [\text{acetal}] [\text{Cr}^{\text{VI}}] [\text{H}^+]^x \quad [1]$$

The value of x is found to be different for different mineral acids as well as for different acetals.

It can be justifiably assumed that the chromic acid oxidation of acetals proceeds through the formation of a transition state involving the acetal and HCrO₄⁻ species, because a plot of $1/k_1$ vs $1/[\text{acetal}]$ is linear without any intercept on the Y-axis¹⁰. The transition state may be visualised as an entity in which the electron-deficient chromium of HCrO₄⁻ is coordinated to the oxygen atom of the alkoxy group of the acetal. In the rate-determining slow step such a species undergoes electron rearrangement to give the product ester and chromium species.

The electron-withdrawing substituents such as NO₂, Cl at the *meta*- and *para*-positions increase the rate of oxidation while electron-releasing substituent OCH₃ at the *para*-position considerably retards the reaction (Table 1). Hammett's correlations on the oxidation of *meta*- and *para*-substituted acetals show a small positive ρ value for the reaction ($\rho=0.4$). The small positive value of ρ may be attributed to the cyclic nature of the transition state involved in the reaction.

The following mechanism is proposed (Scheme 1).

Products

Scheme 1

The isokinetic temperature computed from the plot of ΔH^\ddagger vs ΔS^\ddagger is 313 K. The changes in the rate of oxidation of aromatic acetals by Cr^{VI} are governed by changes in both enthalpy and entropy of activation, which is shown by the linear correlation between the activation enthalpies and entropies ($r=0.9998$). The negative entropy of activation lends support to this mechanism based on charge separation in the transition state. When two reacting molecules combine to form a single activated complex, the restriction on their motion obviously increases as they can no longer move independently, resulting in a large negative entropy of activation.

The plots of log k_2 vs the reciprocal of the dielectric constant of the solvent for the oxidation of BnBA are linear with a positive slope, which suggests that one of the reacting species is a positive ion.

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References

1. D. L. HRYWOOD and B. PHILLIPS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 1699.
2. N. XAVIER and S. J. ARULRAJ, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1984, **93**, 1281.
3. I. ALPHONSE and S. J. ARULRAJ, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1985, **24**, 199.
4. N. XAVIER and S. J. ARULRAJ, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1995, **24**, 519.
5. S. J. ARULRAJ, *Indian J. Chem.*, communicated.
6. S. J. ANGYAL and K. JAMES, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1971, **24**, 1219.
7. S. J. ANGYAL and M. E. EVANS, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, **25**, 1513.
8. K. NAGARAJAN, S. SUNDARAM and N. VENKATASUBRAMANIAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1979, **18**, 360, 395.
9. J. ROCHK and F. HASAN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 3181.
10. J. S. LEVIT, *Tetrahedron*, 1971, **27**, 81.